

Questions to CETAQUA

Interview with Lucia Jimena Gonzalez and Pedro Villanueva, BioReCer project coordinators and leaders of Work Package 2

As part of WP2 in Project BioReCer, what key sustainability and circularity indicators are being used to assess biological resources? How were these indicators selected, and why are they important to the project?

The selection of indicators was based on the development of a fundamental theoretical framework, in which key principles and criteria were established to assess sustainability and circularity. This was based on an extensive literature review, which examined certification schemes, European directives, standards, and initiatives.

This was further combined with the principles set out in the ISO 59000 series of standards. These standards outline methodologies for measuring resource-use efficiency, waste reduction, and impacts throughout the life cycle, providing a foundation for assessing the performance of products and organisations.

After establishing this foundation, the indicators were adapted to the context of biological resources and the associated industries.

How do you ensure that the sustainability and circularity indicators are applicable and useful for all stakeholders, including biomass producers, certification authorities, and consumers?

Within the project, we have the involvement of several partners representing these stakeholders, allowing the indicators to be tested as they are developed, and ensuring that they are measurable, specific, and reflect the reality of the context in which they are applied.

Regarding the validation of the indicators, how are you ensuring that the data used to assess the sustainability and circularity criteria is reliable and verifiable?

As mentioned earlier, through some partners involved in the project, we have access to real data provided by various organisations, industries and companies.

At the same time, one of the central aspects of our project is the traceability of biological resources throughout the value chain. Therefore, we are working directly with these stakeholders to understand the control and traceability mechanisms they currently have in place and how we can integrate them with the applications we are developing to automate data collection and ensure the accurate calculation of the designed indicators.

How do the sustainability and circularity indicators you are developing align with European regulations, such as the EU Taxonomy Regulation, to ensure consistency and acceptance of bio-based products in the market?

Directly, the developed indicators focus on the goal of promoting the transition to a circular economy, which is one of the environmental objectives of the EU Taxonomy Regulation.